

**REDUCTION OF COMPOSITES COST
BY
PUTTING GLOBAL QUALITY INTO ACTION**

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ABSTRACT

The basis of Total Quality is the principle that every business activity is a process that you can measure and continuously improve. The way to reduction of composite cost is through your employees and customers.

1. REDUCTION OF MANUFACTURING COST

In Today's environment, the reduction of Manufacturing cost goes right along with producing a quality product and customer satisfaction.

The control of your manufacturing process is the key to cost reduction. There are three basic steps to achieve this.

1. An ordered sequence of steps; performed by a function of the organization to control input into output and meet the intended objectives.
2. The process must be performed continuously (repetitively) with predictable results.
3. Results are measured against objectives to quantify process performance.

1.1. WHAT IS A WORLD CLASS COMPANY

A World class company:

- Performs it's few critical processes with quantum advantages (in cost, in schedule, and quality) over it's competitors.
- Measures it's performance against the best in the world.

1.1.1 TYPICAL

- Most processes today fail to meet required performance metrics, producing about 6,210 defects per million attempts (SIGMA-4).

However, you tend to doubt these figures, these unbelievable improvements are what world class companies achieve.

The key to this type of improvement is to know exactly where your company stands relative to your competition. This is accomplished by developing a detailed set of metrics (benchmark) that can be compared to the best in the world.

1.1.2 KEY TO GLOBAL QUALITY

Your company needs to develop a set of recommended process improvements driven by the company's goals and objectives. You take today's processes and develop common processes.

The key to global quality:

- Pay attention to the process.
- Involve employees in the process.
- Pay attention to the customer.

This concept especially applies to the processes that are required to produce composite parts.

The corporate landscape is shifting fast. Competition is increasingly global, technology is developing quickly, and the work force is changing profoundly.

Companies must concentrate on their core competencies - what they do best and what differentiates them from the competition.

The company who succeeds in the future with low cost composite parts, will be the one who today is working on process improvement.

The proven approach by "World Class" corporation is:

- Structured, traceable process improvement prioritization - driven by mission/goals/business influences.
- Quantum leap and common process opportunities.
- Bringing about cultural change strategies.
- Investigation of common practices, benchmarking and TQM approaches.

The results of your investigation should bring about traceable goals/objectives, optimum use of resources, focus on major impacts, improved processes and create inter-organization solutions.

1.1.3 THE WAY TO REDUCTION OF COMPOSITE COST

The manufacture of composite products today is labor intensive, coupled with the high cost of material such as graphite/epoxy. The only way to cut cost is by process improvement.

- Improving the process means doing it right the first time and every time thereafter.

- Improving quality will reduce cost and create customer satisfaction.
- Empower your employees to reduce cost and improve quality.

Then and only then will you become a producer of world class composite parts.

PRACTICAL DESIGN

